

Notes

Proton-Ligand Formation Constants and Formation Constants of Some Tl(I)-Amino Salicylates.

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COMPLEXING tendencies of Tl(I) with 4-amino salicylic (4-ASA) and 5-amino salicylic (5-ASA) acid have been studied in the present work. Proton ligand formation constants required for the calculation of formation constants were determined under the same experimental conditions employing half integral (HI), linear plot (LP), and point-wise calculation (PC) methods. Refined values of formation constants were also calculated by the method of least-squares (LS).

Experimental

pH-metric titrations of solutions of (i) free HClO_4 , (ii) free HClO_4 + ligand and (iii) free HClO_4 + ligand + Tl(I), were performed in 50% (V/V) aqueous ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1M (NaClO_4).

The experimental set up and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier⁷⁻⁹.

Results and Discussion

The Irving-Rossotti expression¹⁰ was used for the calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$. In calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$, the concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume as a result of addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and $p(L)$ corresponding to different B-values (pH -meter readings) were calculated and formation curves were obtained for ligands and complexes by plotting \bar{n}_A vs. pH and \bar{n} vs. $p(L)$ respectively.

The values of $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_3^H$ were directly read from the proton ligand formation curves by half integral method. Linear plot and pointwise calculation methods were also used for calculating proton ligand formation constants (Table-1). Results clearly indicate the protonated nature of amino group. Values are in agreement with the resonance, inductive and steric effect of the groups in the two cases and are comparable to the values of other substituted salicylic acids under the same experimental conditions⁸ and also to the values of other workers. In the present cases, values of $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_3^H$ correspond to protonation of phenoxide, amino, and carboxylate group respectively.

In both the cases, \bar{n} value never exceeds 1.75, indicating thereby the formation of only 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were directly read from the formation curves as $p(L)$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 corresponding to $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively. Formation constants were also calculated by employing linear plot and pointwise calculation method. Refined values of formation constants were obtained by the method of least squares (Table-2). The order of formation constant is in agreement with the basicities of the ligands. The values are higher than that of nitro derivatives^{1,2,4-6} which may be due to less steric hindrance of amino group in comparison to nitro group¹¹ for Tl(I) ion.

In view of very low concentration of Tl(I) ion ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) used in the titration, formation of polynuclear complexes may be ignored.

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS

METHOD	4-ASA			5-ASA		
	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_3^H$	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_3^H$
HI	10.92	5.96	2.80	11.00	5.45	2.80
LP	10.94	5.95	2.80	10.99	5.43	2.80
PC	11.20	5.94	2.78	11.66	5.45	2.72
AVERAGE	11.02	5.95	2.79	11.22	5.44	2.77

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-COMPLEXES

METHOD	Tl(I)-4-ASA		Tl(I)-5-ASA	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
HI	7.40	5.50	7.88	5.32
LP	7.30	5.55	7.86	5.34
PC	7.36	5.51	7.91	5.42
LS	7.32	5.54	7.88	5.36
AVERAGE	7.36	5.52	7.88	5.36

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Calorie and Amino Acid Composition of *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* Seeds

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CUCURBITA pepo and *Cucumis melo* seeds are found to be rich in calorie, proteins and all protein bound essential amino acids except tryptophane.

Cucurbita pepo and *Cucumis melo* belong to the family "Cucurbitaceae". As described by Kirtikar and Basu¹, their fruit and mature seeds possess several medicinal properties. These seeds are used as nerve tonic. Because of little published information on the subject, high calorie and protein contents of these seeds, the nutritional characteristics of their protein isolates are investigated and reported in this communication.

Experimental

Proximate chemical composition was determined by standard methods²⁻³. The results are given in table 1.

TABLE 1—PROXIMATE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF *Cucurbita pepo* AND *Cucumis melo* SEEDS

SEEDS	Per 100 g. of edible portion						Calorie
	Mois- ture	Fats	Proteins	Fibre	Ash	Carbohydr- ates	
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	8.4	49.2	26.2	0.5	4.2	11.6	655
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	7.2	48.7	30.6	0.5	5.3	7.6	640

The coarsely ground seeds were defatted with petroleum ether (B.P. 60-80°) and the seed meals were analysed for N-contents. The seed meals of *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* were found to contain 66.8 and 68.2 percent of proteins. The defatted seeds were repeatedly extracted with cold alkaline 10% brine for several hours and filtered. The filtrate, on adjustment of pH-value between 3.5-4.5, precipitated proteins in yields 21.8 and 21.6% respectively from *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* seeds respectively. Proteins were hydrolysed completely by refluxing with a mixture of 6N.HCl and 80% formic acid taken in 1:1 ratio by volume and the hydrolysate concentrated to syrupy consistency by evaporation which was vacuum desiccated⁴. The mass was then dissolved in 10% isopropanol and qualitatively analysed by uni and two dimensional circular and vertical paper (Whatman No 1) and cellulose thin layer chromatographic techniques⁵⁻¹¹ using (1) n-butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:1.6); (2) pyridine: water (4:1); (3) n-butanol: pyridine:

TABLE 2—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF PROTEIN ISOLATES OF *Cucurbita pepo* AND *Cucumis melo* SEEDS

(Amino acid percentage expressed in g/16 g of nitrogen)

% of Amino acid	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	<i>Cucumis melo</i>
<i>Indispensable</i>		
1. Lysine	6.14	4.63
1. Histidine	1.56	1.44
3. Threonine	7.2	6.4
4. Phenylalanine	6.02	7.40
5. Valine	9.0	9.8
6. Methionine	2.8	0.8
7. Tryptophane	0.3	0.4
8. Leucine and isoleucine	12.9	13.4
<i>Semi-Indispensable</i>		
9. Serine*	5.2	4.3
10. Glycine (indispensable for chicks)	8.4	8.1
11. Tyrosine †	4.2	1.42
12. Cystine ‡	0.4	0.6
13. Arginine (indispensable both for rats and chicks)	14	14.1
<i>Dispensable</i>		
14. Glutamic acid	10.2	11.8
15. Aspartic acid	6.2	8.2
16. Alanine	6.1	8.4
17. Proline §	0.8	0.5
18. γ -Amino butyric acid	Traces	Traces

Mean values of 10 determinations

- * Serine exerts sparing effect upon glycine.
 † Tyrosine exerts sparing effect upon phenylalanine.
 ‡ Cystine exerts sparing effect upon methionine.
 § Optical density measured at 440 nm.